

Studies on Prothrombin time and Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time in Medical Radiographers Exposed to Radiation in Imo State, Nigeria

*Nnadozie Agatha C¹., Aloy-Amadi Oluchi C¹., Okoroiwu L. I¹., Iheanacho M.C², and Eleonu Chinedu P. ³

¹Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria.

²Department of Haematology and Blood Transfusion, Federal Teaching Hospital, Owerri, Nigeria.

³Department of Public Health Management, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: [Nnadozie Agatha C.](#)

Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria.

Abstract

Medical radiographers are frequently exposed to ionizing radiation, which can have significant biological effects, including alterations in haemostatic parameters. Prolonged exposure to radiation may lead to haematological changes, affecting coagulation pathways and increasing the risk of thrombotic or haemorrhagic disorders. This study was a cross-sectional study aimed at determining the levels of some haemostatic parameters among medical radiographers, providing insights into potential risks and emphasizing the need for enhanced radiation protection measures. The study was carried out at three major hospitals in Imo State (Federal Teaching Hospital, Owerri, Imo specialist hospital, Umuguma, Owerri and Imo State Teaching Hospital, Orlu). A total of 40 individuals which comprised of 40 radiographers and 40 non-radiation workers were recruited for the study. Informed consent was obtained from each patient and demographic features and history obtained using questionnaire before sample collection. The procedure was carried out using standard laboratory procedures, and the results of the tests were analyzed using SPSS version 2. The mean values of PT (14.68 ± 2.59) secs and APTT (36.81 ± 5.95) secs in medical radiographers were significantly prolonged when compared to controls (12.23 ± 1.62) secs and (28.82 ± 5.23) secs ($p = 0.000$). The degree of prolongation was more pronounced in radiographers with longer exposure durations, suggesting cumulative effects of radiation on coagulation pathways. In conclusion, prolonged PT and APTT among medical radiographers suggest that chronic radiation exposure may contribute to coagulation dysfunction, increasing the risk of haemorrhagic complications. This highlights the need for continuous monitoring of haemostatic parameters in radiographers to ensure early detection and management of potential coagulation disorders.

Keywords: Prothrombin Time, Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time, Radiographers, Radiation.

1. Introduction

Radiation in the form of electromagnetic radiation refers to energy transferred from one place to another and maybe ionizing or non-ionizing depending on the amount of energy it possesses (Jaffee *et al.*, 2020). X-ray is a form of ionizing radiation that is found useful in medical imaging.

Radiographers as radiation workers are exposed to low doses of ionizing radiation during radiological procedures (Rozaj *et al.*, 2019). Ionizing radiation can induce various forms of cell damage, including the possibility of increasing the incidence of chromosomal aberration. Cytotoxic effects of low dose ionizing radiation in occupationally exposed radiation workers were recorded in several earlier studies (Fleming *et al.*, 2020).

The coagulation pathway is a cascade of events that leads to haemostasis. The intricate pathway allows for rapid healing and prevention of spontaneous bleeding. Two paths, intrinsic and extrinsic, originate separately but converge at a specific

point, leading to fibrin activation. The purpose is to ultimately stabilize the platelet plug with a fibrin mesh (Macfarlane, 2020).

The concept of a stepwise process or cascade of the coagulation system was first described in 1964 (Lippi *et al.*, 2019). While this traditional model described two separate pathways, the intrinsic and the extrinsic pathway, which culminate in a common pathway, current views support an interconnected relationship between the two (Masumura *et al.*, 2022). The contact pathway (also called the kallikrein–kinin system) is composed of three zymogens [factor XII (FXII), plasma kallikrein (PK), and high-molecular-weight kininogen (HMWK)]. In vitro, the initial triggering event leads to clot formation through the activation of FXII on an artificial surface.

Prothrombin Time sometimes called (PT) is a test to evaluate blood clotting. Prothrombin is a protein produced by the liver. It is one of the many haemostatic factors in your blood that helps to clot appropriately. Activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) is a screening test that helps evaluate a person's ability to appropriately form blood clots. It assesses the amount and function of certain proteins in the blood (Ogedegbe *et al.*, 2022). Prothrombin Time (PT) and Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (APTT) are critical assays used to evaluate the extrinsic and intrinsic pathways of the coagulation cascade, respectively. Prolongation of these parameters can indicate coagulopathies, which may predispose individuals to bleeding complications. Previous studies have demonstrated that exposure to proton radiation can lead to significant increases in PT and APTT values, suggesting potential radiation-induced coagulopathy (Davis *et al.*, 2012). However, there is a paucity of research specifically examining these effects in medical radiographers. This study aims to assess whether chronic occupational radiation exposure in radiographers is associated with significant prolongation of PT and APTT compared to non-exposed individuals and to evaluate the correlation between exposure duration and these hemostatic parameters.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted at the Federal Teaching Hospital, Owerri, Imo Specialist Hospital, Umuguma, Owerri, and Imo State University Teaching, Hospital (IMSUTH) Orlu, all in Imo State .

2.2 Study Design

This research was a cross-sectional study carried out at three major hospitals in Imo State (Federal University Teaching Hospital, Owerri, Imo specialist hospital, Umuguma, Owerri and Imo State Teaching Hospital, Orlu). A total of 40 individuals which comprised of 40 radiographers and 40 non - radiation workers were recruited for the study. Informed consent and questionnaires were administered before sample collection, and two milliliters of venous blood was collected from each subject, and dispensed into citrated container, for the estimation of PT and APTT. The procedure was carried out using standard laboratory procedures, and results of the tests were analyzed using SPSS version 27.

2.3 Method of Recruitment

Medical radiographers between the ages of 30 - 60yrs who were working with the three hospitals and gave their informed consents were recruited for the study. Age-matched non-exposed subjects served as controls. Strict confidentiality was maintained.

2.4 Study Population

A total of forty (40) radiographers and an equivalent number of age- matched non-exposed subjects consisted the study population.

2.5 Ethical Approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethics committee of Federal Teaching Hospital, Owerri, Imo state Teaching Hospital, Orlu and Imo state Specialist Hospital Umuguma. All study participants who gave their informed consent were enrolled in the study before sample collection.

3. Laboratory Analysis

The PT and APTT were estimated using CA – 101 sysmex.

3.3.2 Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 27 (statistical packages for social sciences). All values were expressed as mean± standard deviation. The student-t-test and Pearson correlation were used to determine the differences in the experimental variables. The tests with a probability $P \leq 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

4. Results

Table 1: Mean Values of Prothrombin (PT) and Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (APTT) in Radiographers (Test) and Non-Radiographers (Control)

The PT (14.68±2.59)secs and APTT (36.81±5.95)secs in radiographers were significantly prolonged when compared to controls (12.23±1.62)secs and (28.82±5.23)secs (t=5.07,p=0.000 and t=6.38 , p=0.000).

Parameter	Test	Control	t-value	p-value
PT (secs)	14.68±2.59	12.23±1.62	5.07	0.000*
APTT (secs)	36.81±5.95	28.82±5.23	6.38	0.000*

KEY:

PT: Prothrombin

APTT: Activated Prothrombin

*: Significant p value

Table 2: Mean Values of PT and APTT based on Duration of Exposure.

During 3-10 years of exposure, PT (13.56±1.22) secs, and APTT (35.24±5.58) secs showed no significant difference in time when compared to 11-18years (15.08±2.86) secs and (37.33±6.49) secs and >18years exposure (15.20±3.33) secs and 36.61±5.98 (f=1.39, p=0.264; 0.41, p=0.668).

Parameter	(3-10)yrs	(11-18)yrs	(>18)yrs	f-value	p-value
PT (secs)	13.56±1.22	15.08±2.86	15.20±3.33	1.39	0.264
APTT (secs)	35.24±5.58	37.33±6.49	36.61±5.98	0.41	0.668

Key:

PT: Prothrombin time

APTT: Activated partial thrombin time

Table 3: Mean Values of PT and APTT in Radiographers based on Sex.

There was no significant difference in the mean values of PT (14.62±2.66) secs and APTT (36.79±6.23) secs in males when compared to females (15.38±1.92) secs and (36.10±3.45) secs (t=1.43,p=0.810; t = 1.37, p= 0.672).

Parameter	Male	Female	t-value	p-value
PT (secs)	14.62±2.66	15.38±1.92	1.43	0.810
APTT (secs)	36.79±6.23	36.10±3.45	1.37	0.672

KEY:

PT: Prothrombin time

APTT: Activated partial thrombin time

Table 4: Comparison of PT and APTT in Radiographers based on Age.

There was non-significant difference in the mean values of PT (14.71±2.57) secs, and APTT (37.62±5.91) secs, in radiographers of ages (35-50)yrs when compared to those of ages >50 yrs (14.64±1.08) secs, and (34.90±5.91) secs (t=0.62, p=0.16; t=0.24, p=0.178).

Parameter	(35-50) yrs n=27	>50 yrs n=13	t-value	p-value
PT (secs)	14.71±2.57	14.64±1.08	0.62	0.161
APTT (secs)	37.62±5.91	34.90±5.91	0.24	0.178

KEY:

PT: Prothrombin time

APTT: Activated partial thrombin time

5. Discussion

Long-term exposure to low doses of ionizing radiation has been reported to have adverse effects on the human cells especially that of the radiation workers, these effects may result in various hematological, haemostatic and biochemical disorders (Davoudi *et al.*, 2022).

The current study reveals that there was a significant prolongation of PT and APTT in radiographers when compared to controls. The increased PT and APTT indicates increased bleeding time and low platelet and coagulation parameters

which is as a result of exposure to radiation particles (Meo, 2022). Coagulation is a very organized process involving the interaction of endothelial cells, platelets and coagulation factors. Abnormal coagulation appears to be an important issue among radiographers. The result from this study is in agreement with the study carried out by Dou *et al.*, (2021), who reported that recent data support that medical radiographers are at high risk of developing disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) or even death due to altered coagulation parameters.

There was no significant difference in the mean values of PT and APTT in radiographers when compared based on the duration of exposure. This finding is consistent with the findings of the studies conducted Yang *et al.*, (2019), who reported no significant changes in the mean values of platelet count, prothrombin time among radiation workers. The absence of significant differences in Prothrombin Time (PT) and Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (APTT) values among medical radiographers, regardless of exposure duration, suggests that chronic occupational exposure to ionizing radiation may not adversely affect these specific hemostatic parameters. This finding aligns with the understanding that PT and APTT are primarily influenced by deficiencies or dysfunctions in specific clotting factors, liver disease, vitamin K deficiency, or the presence of anticoagulants (Krigsfeld *et al.*, 2012).

It is important to note that while some studies have reported increased clotting times due to radiation exposure, these effects were observed under conditions of high-dose radiation or in experimental settings that may not directly correlate with occupational exposures experienced by radiographers. The lack of significant alterations in PT and APTT among radiographers with varying exposure durations may be attributed to effective radiation safety protocols and protective measures in place within medical facilities. These protocols are designed to minimize radiation exposure and its potential health effects (Krigsfeld *et al.*, 2012).

In comparison of these haemostatic parameters among medical radiographers based on sex and age, this study revealed that there were no significant changes in the mean values, indicating that age and sex of these professionals have no effect on these parameters. The result is in agreement with the study carried out by Khorrami and Riahi-Zanjani (2020), who reported a similar finding.

6. Conclusion

This study has shown that prolonged PT and APTT among medical radiographers suggest that chronic radiation exposure may contribute to coagulation dysfunction, increasing the risk of haemorrhagic complications. This highlights the need for continuous monitoring of haemostatic parameters in radiographers to ensure early detection and management of potential coagulation disorders.

References

1. Ann R.kennedy, Anit Maity and Jenine k.Sanzari (2016). A review of radiation reduced coagulopathy and new findings to support pointal prevention strategies and treatments; National library of Medicine, Radiat Res., Jul 26;186(2): 121-140 doi: 10,1667/RRI4406.1
2. Ariens, R.A.S., Khoher, H.P., Mansfield, M.W., Grant, P.J. (2018). Subunit Antigen and Antibody Levels of Blood Coagulation Factor XIII in Healthy Individuals. *Arthrosclerosis thrombovascular biology* 19:212-216.
3. Arthur, G., John, E.H. (2020). Haemochromatosis and blood coagulation, mechanism of blood coagulation, Blood coagulation test. *Medical Physiology*; 5: 457-467.
4. Bolliger, D., Seeberger, M.D., Tanaka, K.A. (2018). Principles and practice of thromboelastography in clinical coagulation management and transfusion practice. *Transfusion medicine reviews* 26: 1–13.
5. Davis L.K, Moyer B.R and Riley R.M(2012). The effects of proton radiation on the Prothrombin and Partial Thromboplastin times in ferrets. *International Journal of Radiation of Biology*;88(2):135-142.
6. Davoudi, M., Keikhaei, B. and Tahmasebi, M. (2022). Hematological profile change in radiation field workers. *Apadana Journal of Clinical Research*;1(1): 38-44.
7. Dou, L., Tao, X., Zhao, W., Zheng, G., Lu, Y., Tong, W., et al. (2021). shRNA targeting nonstructural protein inhibits the replication of severe fever with thrombocytopenia syndrome virus. *Future Virology*. 16: 451–458.
8. Favalaro, E.J., Lippi G. (2020). Coagulation update: What's new in hemostasis testing? *Thrombosis Research* 127: 13–16.
9. Fleming, T., Peiris-John, R., Crengle, S. and Archer, D. (2020). Youth19 Rangatahi Smart Survey, Initial Findings: Introduction and Methods. The Youth19 Research Group, The University of Auckland and Victoria University of Wellington, *New Zealand*; 45-78.
10. Jaffee, S.R., Sligo, J.L., McAnally, H.M. and Bolton, A.E. (2020). Early-onset and recurrent depression in parents increases risk of intergenerational transmission to adolescent offspring. *Journal of Child Psychology Psychiatry*;56.
11. Khorrami, M.B. and Riahi-Zanjani, B. (2020). Hematological profile of healthy workers exposed to low dose radiation. *Pharmacology Online*. 2:138-141.
12. Krigsfeld G.S, Sanzari J.K, Kennedy A.R(2012). The effects of proton radiation on the prothrombin and partial thromboplastin times in ferrets. *International journal of radiation of biology*;88(2):135-142.

13. Lippi, G., Favaloro, E.J., Franchini, M. and Guidi, G.C. (2019). Milestones and perspectives in coagulation and hemostasis. *Seminar on Thrombosis Haemostasis*. 35(1):9–22.
14. Macfarlane, R.G. (2020). An enzyme cascade in the blood clotting mechanism, and its function as a biochemical amplifier. *Nature*;202: 498–499.
15. Masumura, K., Kuniya, K., Kuroba, T. and Fukuoka, M. (2022). Ion-induced mutations in the gpt delta transgenic mouse: comparison of mutation spectra induced by heavy-ion, X-ray, and gamma-ray radiation. *Environmental Molecular Mutagen*;44 (2): 9.
16. Meo, S.A. (2022). Hematological findings in male x-ray technicians. *Saudi Medical Journal*; 25(7): 852-856.
17. Nnamani N.A, Anthony U.E, Idris A.N, Adamu Babayo and Emmanuel K.U(2014). Evaluation of PT and APTT in hypertensive pts attending a tertiary hospital in Calabar, Nigeria; *Advances in Hematology*; Nov 16: 2014: 932039.doi:10.1155/2014/932039.
18. Ogedegbe, H.O. (2022). An overview of hemostasis. *Laboratory Medicine* 33: 948–953.
19. Rozaj, R., Kasuba, V. and Sentija, K. (2019): Radiation-induced chromosomal aberrations and hematological alterations in hospital workers. *Occupational Medicine*; 49 (6): 353-360.
20. Wagner, R., Meyerriecks, N. and Berman, C.Z. (2017). In vitro effects of x-radiation on white blood cells and blood platelets. *Blood*; 12(8): 733-745.
21. Yang, F.E., Vaida, F. and Ignacio, L. (2019). Analysis of weekly complete blood counts in patients receiving standard fractionated partial body radiation therapy. *International Journal of Radiation and Oncology Biology*;33(3): 617.